

Post-Neoliberal Theologies of Technology

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In this piece, I want to combine several strands into a single thesis: First, that an ethical machine needs to have an appropriate character, for which there are abundant philosophical sources. Second, that as alienated postmodern beings, humans have become epistemologically detached and are searching for a new theology. Third, that machines may provide that new theology, the ultimate manifestation of enlightenment righteousness, a dogmatic and absolutist scientism: transcendent historical materialism.

Appropriate Ethics: The Good Leader versus The Good Market

In considering ethical machines, we are forced in the first instance to consider what an appropriate ethics might be. Leaving aside for now the question of objective right and modern humanist hubris, it is useful to begin by considering how an appropriately ethical human leader might behave. It might be posited that an appropriately ethical human leader have *character*, a kind of sensibility that we as subjects substantially agree is good, or desirable. There is a tension between selfish interest, an interest in self-preservation, and a more generous, even altruistic social interest, one of social preservation, a defence of community.

In establishing late-modern capitalist systems of government in the western liberal tradition (so much baggage in those few words!) political scientists, philosophers and legal framers have sought to empower leaders while minimising the possibility of corruption or self-dealing. Constructs such as the separation of powers, term limits and elections serve as examples, though their effectiveness has varied from state to state. The potential for the leader to enrich or further empower themselves or their families is perpetually in conflict with their role as a public representative, tasked with the improvement of the social position.

Much of the neoliberal establishment sought to avoid this kind of conflict altogether, by assuming that all (human) leaders will by default act selfishly; that is how human beings are programmed, and any attempt to drive alternate behaviour is foolish. Therefore the power given to people through structures of government must be small, while market forces drive resource distribution and social organisation to the maximum extent possible (Hayek, 2007).

Character, *Thumos* and the Machine

The character of the good leader has been the subject of philosophers and writers for as long as we have records. The distinction between the perfidious selfish ruler and the altruistic noble king is one that in some ways cleaves history and ontology in an eternal dichotomy: it is the distinction between self and other, and by extension between reason and faith. Is it possible for a person to truly believe in anything other than herself? This gets to the essence of identity, of existence, of meaning.

In Homer, the concept of *thumos* (Homer, 2003) most often translated as 'spiritedness', echoes this kind of human motivation to do good in the world. Jonathan Shay describes *thumos* as reflecting '...how well or badly those who hold power fulfil the culture's moral order.' (Beston et al., 2018) In a sense the concept of honour can be associated with

thumos. Plato distinguished *thumos* from *eros*, or erotic love, a more base self-centered drive (Plato & Lee, 1987). Beyond this distinction and aligned with the dichotomy are nature and culture, Rousseau's *amour propre* versus his *amour de soi même* (Rousseau, 1993), and even it is to be suggested a distinction between communication and language (Wittgenstein, 1958). These distinctions have a consistent divide between self and other.

What then should be the character of the machine? Clearly a machine is not capable of thumotic drives, nor is it driven by honour. What are its drives? Can they be coded? There are two important perspectives to be considered in evaluating the *character* of the machine: first, the disposition of the machine towards its subjects, towards those over whom it bears a power, such as in resource distribution or judgement. Second, there is the disposition of the subjects towards the machine, and how they perceive the machine in their lives. Langdon Winner has pointed out in his famous essay 'Do Artifacts Have Politics?' (Winner, 1986), that it would be mistaken to consider whether things in themselves had politics – that such was the exclusive preserve of the human. While object-oriented ontologists may demur on the point, I will focus on the outside in view for illumination.

The Death of Expertise and the Epistemological Wasteland

The demise of liberal idealism characterised by the Brexit vote in the United Kingdom and the election of Donald Trump in the United States have been blamed in many quarters on technology. The internet, and its ad-tech mavens, the wielders of influence over the simple minds of manipulable peoples, had conspired to undermine the basic principles of democracy using its own tools. How else could rational beings choose to do themselves a harm? How could they willingly, openly choose to puncture the lofty aspirations of *liberté, égalité et fraternité*? Technology had become so advanced that forces as primal as free will could be bent to the desires of powerful interests.

At the same time, the failures in global governance that gave rise to the crash of 2008, the acceleration in income inequality, the climate crisis, sweeping disenfranchisement and a resurgent fascism were causing people to question the system itself. Both the election of Donald Trump and the Brexit result in the UK had people suggesting that 'the system' needed to be destroyed before it could be rebuilt. So called 'experts' were now challenged, and a PhD from Harvard or Cambridge was less likely to get your point of view accepted than a 'friend' post on Facebook.

Tom Nichols, writing in a prescient article in *The Federalist* in 2014, described the phenomenon as 'a Google-fuelled, Wikipedia-based, blog-sodden collapse of any division between professionals and laymen, students and teachers, knowers and wonderers – in other words, between those of any achievement in an area and those with none at all.' (Tom Nichols, 2014) Will Self in late 2019 on the BBC radio show *A Point of View* saw in the decision to share both the Booker Prize and the Turner Prize that year a lack of trust in our own capacity for arbitration. It was, he said 'evidence of a culture that no longer believes in its capacity for meaningful choice, and which, by extension, doubts also its capacity for effective agency. But what is it that makes us so convinced of our capacity as a species to control our future, to make, so to speak, our own destiny?' (Self, 2019) That last question, perhaps, is where our present travails have their root: after decades of species exceptionalism, and centuries of anthropocentrism, an aching realisation has been unfolding: the suggestion that we, in our convention and consensus, may be wrong.

The prospect is a scientific, rational and technological conclusion, borne of emotional, sensory and erotic sensibilities. We can feel deep down in our desires and moods that something is not right, something is broken, that our direction is wrong. It appears as an epistemological crisis, a crisis in meaning, convention and community. The social order appears based on an agreed set of principles that seem to be misconstrued, where deep social pathologies compromise human outcomes and the idea of progress is revealed to be illusory. Tracing it back we find self-referential analyses, through modern science, philosophy, early modern religion and politics, all the way back to the Classical Period. This aching realisation is what Juergen Habermas refers to as *an awareness of what is missing*, something that permeates our entire civics. (Habermas, Reeder, Schmidt, & Cronin, 2010)

Schmitt, Heidegger and the Saviour

This wasteland in which we have found ourselves is less of a development, or a progression, and more of a revelation. Carl Schmitt in his *Political Theology* (Schmitt, 1985) suggested that liberal democracy was no more than a charade, a sentimental and idealised vision of the world. There is no such thing as a liberal democratic government, if at every significant challenge those governments declare a state of emergency. The only time liberal democratic values are important are exactly when the limits of government are tested – and the response of government has invariably been to suspend those values in order to deal with whatever so-called crisis is before them.

Schmitt's *Political Theology* traces the evolution of the theological underpinning of State sovereignty through the enlightenment, to a *juristic-ethical* structure based in natural law, to something '...liberated from miracles and dogmas and based on human understanding and critical doubt.' (Id., p. 39) Along the way, Schmitt argues, a kind of 'natural jurisprudence' was the immediate successor of 'natural theology' before the Enlightenment. Hence Rousseau's *general will* was deified: the sovereign was not merely *of* the people, but morally superior to them in that synthesis of will. This was the *juristic-ethical* structure that ameliorated conservative leaning forces in society, while simultaneously accommodating those of a more liberal disposition. There would be laws; those laws were written down (as had been the scripture); and this *order* would prevail.

Ultimately, however, the persistence of any semblance of a deistic structure was denied by a progression of ideas. Towards the end of the nineteenth century, and the beginning of the twentieth century, Schmitt suggests, the ascendant 'traditional religiosity' was unbalanced by an excessive conservatism, the bourgeois rejection of popular artists and writers, and the tight association of church and state. The battle against God, Schmitt writes, was advanced by influential writers such as the anarchists Proudhon and Bakunin, heralding considered visions of socialism, and communism with a small 'c'. 'The sovereign,' Schmitt continues, 'who in the deistic view of the world, even if conceived as residing outside the world, had remained the engineer of the great machine, has been radically pushed aside. The machine now runs itself.' (p.48)

Mankind had become so distanced from any kind of basic humanity, accelerated by technology, that Heidegger in his final years feared for the future (Heidegger, 1976), as he reacted to the Earthrise photograph, published in 1966. The photo was taken by astronaut William Anders on the Apollo 8 mission that orbited the moon, and showed the earth above the horizon of the moon as the orbiter emerged from the dark side. 'I don't know if you were shocked, but [certainly] I was shocked when a short time ago I saw the pictures of the

earth taken from the moon,' Heidegger said. 'We do not need atomic bombs at all [to uproot us] -- the uprooting of man is already here. All our relationships have become merely technical ones. It is no longer upon an earth that man lives today.' Asked later in what was his final interview what would replace philosophy he immediately replied 'Cybernetics'. In perhaps one of his most quotable moments, he summarised the position – 'Only a god can save us now.'

Towards a Theology of Technology

I suggest that there is a third theology upon us: a technological theology. This comes in three forms. First, State bureaucracies have so atrophied their sense of moral mission, their ethic of civil service, that they have become mere functioning tools, elements of economic models, outlined in blue and red ink on the whiteboards of management consultants, having succumbed to what Juergen Habermas has called *the lure of technocracy*ⁱⁱ (Habermas, 2015). Second, technology mediated communications substantially and fundamentally impoverish social relations, denying utterance its importance, and identity its valueⁱⁱⁱ. This has the effect of marginalising the human, the peripheral, the perverted, and the insane, just as it homogenises discourse, as Giorgio Agamben referenced (Agamben, 2014) in off the cuff remarks as he introduced a lecture entitled *Resistance in Art* in 2014^{iv}. Finally, there is a third more visceral and ritual element to this technological theology: data worship. The transhumanist movement (O'Connell, 2017), surveillance capitalism (Zuboff, 2015), and the impossibility of opposition to the sublime power of big data, with its awesome visions and unquestionable solutionism (Morozov, 2013), all present an emergent reversal of the process of secularization.

Hoisted above the altar is the new Christ, the absolutism of historical materialism, a scientific truth, perhaps in the form of a Tesla Roadster with a mannequin (a fake man) at the wheel ("See Views of SpaceX's Starman Riding a Tesla Roadster in Space! | Space," 2018), to the strains of David Bowie's 'Space Oddity' (ironically a song about a disastrous failure in space).

Just as the Bible moves from myth, to folklore, to tradition, custom, law and ultimately revelation (with the coming of Christ as the Bible's pivotal 'enlightenment'), so this narrative progression is matched with one in our political economy. Our law, in this parallel, is our technology: our online democracy and social networks, our video chats with Australian billeted children, and labour reduced to an API^v call. The question becomes what will be our revelation?

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ⁱ The anarchists generally, in their rejection of hierarchy, attacked both that first and primary subjugation described in Feuerbach's [*The Essence of Christianity*](#), as well as any political ordering that would see man dominating man. This was what Murray Bookchin would later describe as *the ecology of freedom*.

ⁱⁱ Habermas' critique of the European Union, a trilogy beginning with *Europe: The Faltering Project* (2010), and *The Crisis of the European Union* (2012), is essentially grounded in problems of legitimacy and passive endorsement. At its root, however, Habermas' philosophy fundamentally questions our capacity to describe reality, and therefore to understand it, and by extension exert some kind of influence over it – political or otherwise.

ⁱⁱⁱ It is a fundamental miscalculation that there is some objective truth that can render moot the function of subjective judgement. Similarly, any assumption that technologies are devoid of personal or human bias are wrong, however pervasive such assumptions may be. Ron Day's *Indexing It All* (MIT Press, 2014) describes with elegance this folly: '[r]outinely and obsessively we use online resources – whose algorithms and indexes both serve and profit from us in ways that the users are largely unaware – as the way of overcoming the physical and emotional distances that are a consequence of modernity, and in particular capitalist modernity, where markets have become the means and the ends for reasoning, communication, and, increasingly, emotion. These devices have become the governance structures – the “idea” or “concept” – for our human manner of being...which increasingly subsume and subvert the former roles of personal judgement and critique in personal and social being and politics.'

^{iv} '[The] general domination of English in conferences, universities and other places of that kind should not be considered so innocent...[that] English is used as a kind of lingua franca, as Latin was used in Europe in the fifteenth, sixteenth and seventeenth centuries - the analogy is misleading, because Latin did not belong to any particular country, while English is proper to a couple of nations. We should reflect on that.' <https://youtu.be/one7mE-8y9c>, at the start.

^v API – an Application Program Interface, the technical basis upon which Internet 'services' are provided.